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Critical study of the travelogues of Dr Altaf Yousafzai (In The Context of “Thailand kay Rang”, “Nile kay Sang” and “Bakhal-e-Hinduwush Bakhsham”)

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Abstract: Dr. Muhammad Altaf Yusufzai, is an Associate Professor in the Department of Urdu (Hazara University Mansehra). Dr Muhammad Altaf Yusufzai is a well-known Personality of Urdu literature, "Mukhtar Masood ka Asloob", "Urdu Nazam or Nine Eleven", Awaz-e-Dost (Pashto Translation) "Safar Nama “Thailand Kay Rang” second travelogue "Nile Kay Sang" and now his latest travelogue “Bakhal-e-Hinduwush Bakhsham has been published”. The travelogue "Thailand Kay Rang" is the best creative marvel of Dr.Altaf and his fictional style is another quality of "Nile Kay Sang" that gives the creator a prominent place in the world of Urdu travel. Dr. Altaf Yousafzai travelogue "Bakhal-e-Hinduwush Bakhsham “is a historical document of Uzbekistan. The easiest and shortest way to get knowledge about Uzbek history, culture, lifestyle, customs, manners, ethics, values and traditions.

Key Words: Dr Altaf Yousafzai, Thai land kay Rang, Nile kay Sang, Bakhal-e-Hinduwush Bakhsham, History, Culture, lifestyle etc.

Topic:

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(In The Context of Thailand kay Rang, Nile kay Sang and Bakhal-e-
Hinduwush Bakhsham)**

It is impossible to deny the importance of travel. Man has been fond of travelling since the beginning of time. The reason is that man has always been anxious to learn new things. Since ancient times, people have travelled for trade and knowledge.

“A travelogue is a piece of writing or a lecture about a trip or journey. A travelogue is an informational text describing a particular country's culture.”(1)

Travelogue has an important place in Urdu literature. A travelogue is considered a form of creative literature. Raees Ahmed Jafri describes the importance of the travelogue as follows:

“The travelogue is very important from the academic and literary point of view. It is the only type of literature that is closely related to almost all important social sciences.”(2)

While reading Thailand k Rang, the thing which really impressed the reader was the style of Dr Altaf Yousafzai. His sense of humour is outstanding. He makes sense out of words and finds humour in words here are interesting examples:

“Niromun's dress was very simple and in this training of thirty days she changed only three shirts while some of the women's who came with us used to change their clothes three times a day”(3)

Dr. Altaf Yousafzai has the quality that his style has not been biased, He has reflected the style of Thailand's politics and monarchy with neutrality and completely honest attitudes. The economic system devised by the king and the agricultural economic terms applied are noteworthy. There is a monarchy, politics, parliament and military rulers. For this reason, Dr Altaf Yousafzai does not feel alienated even here and the same style is seen in his own country.

Being a Pathan, Dr. Altaf Yousafzai has also mentioned the Pathans there, in an interesting way, their families, neighbourhoods, and cities, besides, he has also mentioned a large number of Pakistanis who have been living in Thailand for a long time and have a prominent position. Particularly, the Muslim population, mosques, community centres and religious activities of Muslims were closely observed and cheerfully described.

The end of the travelogue has made every sensitive reader cry. Thai culture, politics, monarchy and military leadership are also similar to our country, but despite all this, this country has gone ahead and is far ahead of us on the road of development after creating its own name and distinct identity in other countries what is our condition?

Dr Altaf Sahib Writes:

“Now Thailand is famous all over the world and the happy thing is that this knowledge is in a good sense. Then when I think about Pakistan, I bow my head because the people of the world don't remember us in such a good sense. I repeat the words of “Veer Wait

Jo” in my mind and think that we have really destroyed the new wealth and good structure. “(4)

Similarly, the Thai monarchs' love for their people has been skillfully and gracefully portrayed. The relationship of the kings there with the educational institutions and then the comparison of the educational degradation in their own country is also a special thing. Overall, Dr. Altaf Yousafzai is a renowned travelogue writer who has written about his travel experiences in Thailand, using the technique of flashbacks to combine past events and recent observations. His travelogue is not only a beautiful addition to modern travelogue but also a reflection of his own self.

After this travelogue, in "Nile kay Sang", Dr Altaf described Egypt and Egypt's culture, politics, social and economic conditions, as well as religious consciousness, romanticism, humour and internal and external conditions. This All these Factors have not only made it interesting but this travelogue has also become a source of information. Dr Ramisha Qamar Writes:

“The travelogue “The Nile kay Sang” is a very beautiful, engaging, informative travelogue, which reveals the religious, political, civilized, social and educational landscape of Egypt.”(5)

There is one who has only heard the name of Egypt and knows nothing more than that. But after reading this travelogue, every reader claims that he is definitely familiar with the Egyptian civilization and this is the origin of Dr. Altaf Sahib. There is skill and success. Wadi-e-Sina, Masjid Sahaba, Qalo Petra, Saint Catherine, Ancient and Modern Egypt, Nile River, Egyptian culture and women in it, the position of women and other places which have been described together with the present Egypt. By connecting with Egypt, he has shown the skill of his charming style.

Dr Altaf Yousafzai has a great sense of humour. But in this journey, humour is not far, but far behind, only humour is felt with its bitterness. The main reasons for this are poverty, social inequality and backwardness, lack of education, the luxury of the rulers and lack of interest in the development of the people. It also makes you think a lot.

“Outside the hall, the thesis writers were struggling to get their certificates, just like the people of poor countries are trying to outdo each other during the distribution of rations”(6)

“With the salary your government is paying this man, he does the same thing” (7)

In view of the references to the Holy Qur'an and Hadiths Mubarak, the way he has used the skill of perfection to describe historical situations and events, and this perfection becomes the motivation in making the creation interesting and this is the outstanding quality of Dr. Altaf Yousafzai Sahib' style.

The fictional style is another quality of "Nile Kay Sang" which gives the creator a prominent place in the world of Urdu travel. The various scenes and characters of "Nile Kay Sang" make the reader a traveller of unseen worlds.

“I asked him what kind of richness needed for the fun time. Just make friends and sit on the banks of the Nile and buy and offer the baby flower” (8)

Dr. Altaf Yousafzai travelogue “Bakhal-e-Hinduwush Bakhsham” is a historical document of his travel to Uzbekistan. The easiest and shortest way to get information about Uzbek history, culture, lifestyle, customs, manners, ethics, values and traditions. The ultimate source is the study of this travelogue.

Dr. Altaf Yousafzai excellence is also that he chooses romantic places for his travels where everyone wants to visit, every eye

wants to see and every heart wants to enjoy. Dr. Altaf Yousafzai described the flourishing of the valleys of Uzbekistan in such a way that the atmosphere and style of the travelogue also smelled. This is the reason that the atmosphere of the mountains and plains of Uzbekistan does not feel alien at all. I don't know what the reason is, but during the trip to Uzbekistan, Dr. Altaf Yousafzai did not feel any alienation and for us too, these mountains, plains and valleys have been known to us. When he was coming back to Pakistan from Uzbekistan, he describes his personal feelings in these words:

“One month in Uzbekistan would pass so quickly, I didn't even think..... The last class on the last day was not like that. On that day, every eye was tearful and every heart was sad... The tears of Madina, umida and Inayat were not stopping. Words like Allah Hafiz, Khuda Hafiz and Goodbye are not spoken in Uzbekistan, but instead they say “will meet again.”(9)

The travelogue is not a fictional genre at all, but Dr Altaf Yousafzai filled it with the impression of a novel or fiction and made the true colour of this journey even more captivating and noteworthy. The unity of characters, dialogues, scenery and impression keeps the reader in its captivating grip and on top of all this Dr. the color of the sketch adds to the fun of the travelogue. “Bakhal-e-Hinduwush Bakhsham “is not only a travelogue but it has many aspects of past, present and future. This is the historical record that not only we who speak and read Urdu are proud of, but the Uzbek people and Uzbekistan are also proud.

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